

FedSynthesis: A Flower-based Framework for Carbon-Reduced Federated Learning

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Abstract

New machine learning paradigms, such as Federated Learning (FL), have become popular for processing privacy-sensitive information without leaking confidential data to unintended parties in networked settings. However, they introduce additional computation and communication overhead. Such overhead leads to an increase in carbon emissions, threatening the sustainability of systems and jeopardizing net-zero goals. This work proposes a carbon-aware FL framework by extending the Flower framework via the incorporation of customized aggregation strategies for carbon emission reduction. For this purpose, an empirical approach is adopted, which leverages the impact of the carbon emission tracker tool CodeCarbon, allowing for the development of new methods based on measured carbon values. Furthermore, MLFlow, an MLOps tool, is integrated into the framework, enabling users to collect metrics and visualize them. The applicability of this framework is tested on a previously published security scheme and federates its machine learning pipeline. A comparison of this approach against a standard FL setup indicates improvements in carbon reduction.

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1 Introduction

During the last two decades, the advancement of computing technology has provided a drastic boost to the usage of smartphones and Internet of Things (IoT) devices in everyday life [19]. Although this phenomenon has led to new possibilities for analytics and conventional Machine Learning (ML)-based solutions due to the ubiquitous generation and storage of huge amounts of data, transferring such big data from individual devices to a centralized location for processing has become a difficult task. Also, concerns of users regarding their private information are also becoming more apparent [6].

To mitigate such limitations mentioned above, Federated Learning (FL) has emerged as a promising paradigm that enables model training across a set of distributed devices [13]. The main idea behind FL is that instead of sharing their data, each device trains a local model using its own private dataset to compute parameters (*i.e.*, gradients or weights) of its local model. Then, calculated parameters are shared and aggregated to construct a global model, which is distributed to participating devices. Apart from the privacy preservation perspective, an aspect of federated learning that is usually overlooked is the increased carbon footprint of the decentralized training process. There are studies showing that as the number of clients increases in the FL, the total emitted CO_2 increases as well [28]. Hence, it is crucial to minimize this emission while keeping the global model accurate. Minimizing energy output of the training process is one way to achieve this goal, since the emitted CO_2 would be proportional to the energy output. In addition to reducing the total energy emission, another way to achieve higher sustainability is to decrease the average Carbon Intensity (*CI*) factor in a computational process [20]. This factor represents the amount (*i.e.*, mass) of CO_2 released per unit of emitted energy and is primarily determined by characteristics of the power grid (*i.e.*, the ratio of green fuel to fossil fuel). When there are multiple devices with different *CI* factors, it is possible to achieve a “greener” computation by choosing devices with lower *CI* values, assuming that the total energy output stays approximately the same [14].

Even though FL-related studies mostly focus on dimensions of privacy, security, and performance, significant work has been conducted on the carbon footprint of FL [17], thereby motivating researchers to come up with FL frameworks to alleviate these adverse effects of FL for different scenarios, such as cross-device setups [1, 11] or cross-silo deployments [4], while leveraging different techniques like client selection [25] or topological optimization [5]. Nevertheless, due to the growing concerns of sustainability, a need for flexible FL frameworks that consider carbon emissions is imminent. This work proposes an extension to the FL framework termed Flower [3], by developing a customized federation strategy to reduce the overall carbon emission of an FL process. Thus, this paper’s contributions are fourfold:

- Designing three heuristic-based algorithms to estimate carbon emission in subsequent FL rounds.

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- Developing a custom aggregation strategy for Flower by utilizing algorithms designed for a carbon-aware client selection process.
- Implementing an extension to the Flower framework, namely FedSynthesis, by incorporating CodeCarbon¹, a carbon emission tracker, and MLFlow², an MLOps tool for tracking and visualizing ML results. FedSynthesis is a publicly available open-source project³.
- Applying the extended framework on a graph neural network-based anomaly detection model called GATAKU [16] to showcase reduced carbon emission.

2 Background and Related Work

Before outlining the design and implementation of FedSynthesis, background information regarding its components, as well as a brief summary of related work, is provided.

2.1 Related Work in Sustainable FL

From a sustainability perspective, FL has been studied mostly in the energy dimension, such that the FL process is optimized in terms of energy output, especially in the wireless networks domain [27]. In that regard, studies utilized various concepts, including but not limited to edge computing [12], Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) [24], hierarchical split learning [26], to enhance the energy efficiency of FL. Moreover, energy-efficient FL has been applied to a broad range of setups in wireless networks, from IoT devices [2] and B5G/6G systems [23] to satellite-based non-terrestrial networks [8, 18]. Although these studies provide valuable insights and findings for energy-efficient FL, the carbon dimension is mostly overlooked, necessitating special solutions for considering both aspects.

In terms of carbon emissions, FL was first investigated by Qiu et al. in [17]. Afterwards, researchers proposed various FL frameworks to measure and alleviate the adverse effects of FL regarding carbon footprint. FedCarbon [11] and FedGreen [1] presented carbon-efficient solutions for cross-device FL setups with numerous clients. CAFE [4] presents a novel approach for restricting carbon emissions in cross-silo FL setups with multiple data centers, by proposing intelligent client selection techniques. Nevertheless, to the best of the authors' knowledge, these studies do not provide a publicly available repository for testing the frameworks.

Table 1: Frameworks provided in sustainable FL studies

Proposed Solution	Energy Focus	Carbon Focus	Public Repository	Measurement Based	Flexible Framework
FedCarbon [11]	×	✓	×	×	×
FedGreen [1]	×	✓	×	×	×
CAFE [4]	×	✓	×	×	×
FedZero [25]	✓	✓	✓	×	×
Fed2Tier [5]	✓	✓	✓	✓	×
Study in [15]	✓	×	×	✓	✓
FedSynthesis	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

¹CodeCarbon: <https://codecarbon.io/>

²MLFlow: <https://mlflow.org/>

³FedSynthesis: <https://github.com/gokcantali/fed-synthesis>

Among relevant studies with a public codebase, FedZero [25] suggested choosing clients based on the available excess energy to reduce carbon footprint, which could be applied in both cross-silo and cross-device setups. Another one, namely Fed2Tier [5], was provided to include intermediary nodes in a mobile edge computing environment, which improves the energy consumption. However, the former simulates the excess energy component rather than using real-time measurements⁴, while the latter is built more as a tool than a flexible framework, thus allowing only a certain set of algorithms and datasets to be utilized⁵. The study closest to what this paper proposes was found to be [15], which presents a framework that leverages PowerTop for power consumption tracking and MLFlow as an MLOps tool for recording metrics and results. Although it lays out a novel approach and promising results, the focus of the paper is only on energy, not carbon emissions.

To give a structured overview, Table 1 compares FL frameworks that aim for sustainability. One can observe that existing tools do not fulfill all the criteria listed in the table, which is the primary impetus behind this paper.

2.2 Background on FedSynthesis Components

The core part of FedSynthesis, namely the Flower framework, was developed by Beutel et al. [3] as a friendly framework for federating an existing ML project. Not only does the framework allow users to execute an FL scenario on distributed devices, but it also enables a project to be run locally and simulate the FL scenario on a single device by representing each client as a separate process.

CodeCarbon² is an open-source tool for estimating carbon emissions on a computing device during a period of time. The tool utilizes the formula $CO_2 = CI * EC$ to compute carbon emissions, where CI represents the carbon intensity, corresponding to the mass of CO_2 released per unit of energy, and EC represents the energy consumption.

MLFlow³ is an open-source experiment tracking and visualization tool that provides a user-friendly API for integration and a simple UI to view results of performed experiments in an organized manner. MLFlow entails the following four components to ease up an ML workflow: tracking, projects, models, and registry. In the scope of this work, FedSynthesis mainly leverages the tracking and models component of MLFlow. While the former records metrics, parameters, and carbon emissions of the ML process, the latter stores developed models for future use.

3 The Design of FedSynthesis

The main goal of this study is to build a framework for users to adapt their current ML solutions to federate in a sustainable manner. To such end, this paper provides a flexible design that would allow users to develop their own carbon-reduction techniques, tailored to their specific FL scenarios. Before scrutinizing the design and implementation of FedSynthesis, assumptions regarding the system model are given below:

- There is already a deployed FL scheme into which the framework needs to be integrated. In other words, FedSynthesis

⁴FedZero: <https://github.com/dos-group/fedzero>

⁵Fed2Tier: <https://github.com/apoorvaktiv/fed2tier>

has no control over the total number of clients and their locations to execute the client-side ML application.

- The configuration of the FL process is static, meaning that there is a fixed set of values for configuration parameters such as the number of rounds or the ratio of clients to participate in the training phase, which is not determined/optimized by FedSynthesis.
- The ML model used in the FL process is identical across all FL clients in the system, along with the hyperparameters, eliminating any case of model heterogeneity.
- All FL clients are equipped with the same set of network capabilities, with similar levels of bandwidth and transmission power, and the local datasets are generated by the client itself, not requiring any external communication.
- In relation to previous assumptions, the variation of the communication carbon footprint is negligible compared to the emissions caused by client-side computations.

3.1 FedSynthesis Architecture

The essential goal of FedSynthesis is to reduce the emission of CO_2 and equivalent greenhouse gases (hereafter referred to as CO_2 -eq) during an FL pipeline. Since the major factor of CO_2 -eq emission is the local development of ML models, the focus here is on the client selection phase, where customized selection algorithms are developed to prioritize devices that would produce less carbon footprint for the next round.

Given the challenges of estimating the carbon or energy emission for a computation device, utilizing static approaches such as fixing the carbon intensity constant or the emitted energy per CPU cycle before the execution of the pipeline is likely to yield misleading results. Instead, empirical data is leveraged via a carbon emission tracker component, which is installed into every client device, thereby measuring the emitted greenhouse gases during the ML model development. This empirical approach is also robust to physical location change, enabling the application of certain scenarios where the client (e.g., a virtual machine running on the cloud) might be migrated to a different cluster between FL rounds. In case the client application runs on virtualized resources, the possibility of such a scenario is likely given the current trends in cloud computing and cybersecurity, such as moving target defense.

Considering aforementioned concerns, the FedSynthesis framework is designed as illustrated in Figure 1. Note that the drawing displays the architectural design, rather than the implementation itself, which could be performed using different technologies. While the boxes with solid lines (e.g., FL Aggregator) represent existing components, the boxes with dashed lines (e.g., Carbon Tracker) represent the abstract building blocks required for the workflow. While FedSynthesis provides a built-in implementation for these blocks as explained in Section 4, users can freely choose other tools for these components.

The general idea behind FedSynthesis is to include the emitted per-client CO_2 -eq gases in the parameter aggregation phase, in such a way that they are summed for reporting, and stored individually to allow for estimating the next round emissions. While an ML process at Client i produces local weights of the trained model, denoted as \vec{W}^{C_i} , the *Carbon Tracker* in the client module measures

Figure 1: An overview of FedSynthesis architecture

carbon emissions, denoted as $CO_2^{C_i}$. Then, both weights and reported CO_2 -eq values are sent to the FL server, specifically the *FL Aggregator* component. Once in the aggregator component, the vector of CO_2 -eq values of all clients, denoted as $\vec{CO_2} < C_1, C_2, \dots, C_N >$ in Figure 1, are sent to the *Store* component, to be used for future estimations. Simultaneously, the same values are summed and sent to the *MLOps Tool* for tracking and visualization purposes. Afterwards, actual weights of all local models, denoted as $\vec{W} < C_1, C_2, \dots, C_N >$, are aggregated using the customizable *Aggregation Function*, which could be any algorithm that is applicable to a FL setup such as FedAvg, and are sent to the *MLOps Tool* for recording. Meanwhile, by leveraging stored CO_2 -eq values, the customizable *CO₂ Estimation Function* component generates an estimation for the carbon emission in the next round, denoted as $\vec{CO_2} < C_1, C_2, \dots, C_N >$. Based on this estimation, the *Client Selector* module assigns clients individual prioritization coefficients, which are then normalized to sum up to one, and constitute the selection probabilities for clients that will participate in the next FL round.

3.2 Client Selection Algorithm with a Carbon-based Priority

Based on the estimated carbon emission for the next round, priorities to each client are assigned for the selection phase, using the following approach. First, the mean of estimated emissions in the next round across clients is calculated:

$$\hat{e}_\mu^t = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}|} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \hat{e}_k^t \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{K} denotes the set of all available clients. Then, the mean of the next round's estimated emissions is divided by each client's estimated emissions, which gives selection priorities:

$$pr_k^t = \frac{\hat{e}_\mu^t}{\hat{e}_k^t} \quad (2)$$

where pr_k^t denotes the priority of client k for round t .

Finally, priorities across clients are normalized, so that these values would sum up to 1, for selection probabilities:

$$pb_k^t = \frac{pr_k^t}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} pr_k^t} \quad (3)$$

where pb_k^t represents the probability of selection of client k for round t .

Algorithm 1 Carbon-based Client Selection Algorithm

```

1: Input: Estimated emissions for round  $t$ :  $\hat{e}_k^t, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$ 
2: Output: Selection probabilities for round  $t$ :  $pb_k^t, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$ 
3:
4: // Step 1: Compute mean estimated emissions
5:  $\hat{e}_\Sigma^t \leftarrow 0$ 
6: for each client  $k \in \mathcal{K}$  do
7:    $\hat{e}_\Sigma^t \leftarrow \hat{e}_\Sigma^t + \hat{e}_k^t$ 
8: end for
9:  $\hat{e}_\mu^t \leftarrow \hat{e}_\Sigma^t / \mathcal{K}$ 
10:
11: // Step 2: Compute priority for each client and sum them
12:  $pr_\Sigma^t \leftarrow 0$ 
13: for each client  $k \in \mathcal{K}$  do
14:    $pr_k^t \leftarrow \hat{e}_\mu^t / \hat{e}_k^t$ 
15:    $pr_\Sigma^t \leftarrow pr_\Sigma^t + pr_k^t$ 
16: end for
17:
18: // Step 3: Normalize priorities for selection probabilities
19: for each client  $k \in \mathcal{K}$  do
20:    $pb_k^t \leftarrow pr_k^t / pr_\Sigma^t$ 
21: end for
22:
23: Return  $pb_k^t, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$ 

```

The algorithm of the client selection process, given the estimated carbon emission for the next round, is illustrated in Algorithm 1. In Lines 4-9, the estimated mean across clients is computed for round t . Selection priorities, inversely proportional to the estimated emission, are calculated for each client in Lines 11-16. Finally, in Lines 18-21, priorities are normalized and formed into selection probabilities, which are then used in the carbon-aware client sampling logic.

3.3 MLOps Integration

Various MLOps tools have emerged from the need to track experiments, visualize results, and deploy models efficiently. That being said, there is usually a lack of built-in support for FL processes in such tools. Consequently, one needs to put more effort into adopting an MLOps logic into an FL setup. One challenge would be to determine which components would benefit most from such integration. Because the goal is to track the global model and metrics, incorporating MLOps logic into the aggregator (*i.e.*, the server) is a straightforward and necessary approach.

On the other hand, to determine whether clients should adopt any MLOps logic or not requires a thorough examination of the specific setup. In a privacy-sensitive scenario, it is assumed that local datasets contain sensitive data that should not be exposed to other parties. Under such an assumption, acquiring information about local datasets introduces privacy concerns. Furthermore, the

application of privacy preservation techniques, such as secure aggregation or differential privacy, makes it challenging to collect accurate information from clients. Considering these difficulties, FedSynthesis excludes clients from any MLOps flow, and only integrates this flow into the aggregator.

4 FedSynthesis Implementation

The selection of dedicated libraries and tools completes the implementation of FedSynthesis.

4.1 Carbon Estimation Algorithms

The following three algorithms are developed to estimate the CO_2 emission for the next round of the FL process:

4.1.1 Simple Averaging. Here, for each client, the emission for the next round is estimated as the average of reported emissions up until the current round t :

$$\hat{e}_k^t = \frac{1}{t-1} \sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} e_k^\tau \quad (4)$$

where e_k^t represents the *reported* carbon emission for client k at round t , and \hat{e}_k^t represents the *estimated* carbon emission for client k at round t .

4.1.2 Exponential Smoothing. As the name suggests, this method uses the concept of exponential smoothing to estimate the carbon emission for the next round per client. The exponential smoothing formula can be expressed as follows:

$$s^0 = x^0 \quad (5)$$

$$s^t = \alpha x^{t-1} + (1-\alpha)s^{t-1} \quad (6)$$

where s^t and x^t represent the smoothed data and the actual data, respectively, for round t , while α is the smoothing factor varying from 0 to 1, indicating the weight of the actual data.

The carbon emission for the next round is estimated to be the smoothed data for the same round, yielding $\hat{e}_k^t = s^t$. By combining Equation 6 with this value and incorporating reported emissions into the sequence x , the closed-form expression of the estimated emissions, for client k at round t , can be computed as below:

$$\hat{e}_k^t = (1-\alpha)^{t-1} e_k^1 + \alpha \sum_{i=0}^{t-2} (1-\alpha)^i e_k^{t-i} \quad (7)$$

where $e_k^1 = x^0$ since x^0 is the first observed carbon emission data for client k .

4.1.3 Linear Regression. In this method, a linear regression model is trained based on the reported emission values up to the current round. Only two features are used: the round number and the emitted CO_2 -eq value per round. The estimated value for the next round is assumed to be the output of the regression model, which utilizes the formula $\hat{e}_k^t = \hat{\alpha}_k + t\hat{\beta}_k$ with $\hat{\alpha}_k$ and $\hat{\beta}_k$ being computed as:

$$\hat{\alpha}_k = \frac{\sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} e_k^\tau}{t-1} - \frac{t}{2} \hat{\beta}_k \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{\beta}_k = \frac{\sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} (\tau - \frac{t}{2})(e_k^\tau - e_k^\mu)}{\sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} (\tau - \frac{t}{2})^2} \quad (9)$$

where e_k^μ represents the average emission for client k :

$$e_k^\mu = \frac{\sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} e_k^\tau}{t-1} \quad (10)$$

4.2 Carbon Tracker

For carbon footprint estimation, CodeCarbon is chosen as the tool for tracking the carbon emission by client models. CodeCarbon is a widely adopted tool that periodically queries computational resources (e.g., CPU, memory, storage) to measure the energy spent during a period of time. For estimating the carbon intensity of a device, CodeCarbon relies on a fixed list of carbon intensity values corresponding to countries/regions, and by inferring the physical location through the IP address, it provides an educated guess. Furthermore, more fine-grained information on carbon intensity values is available for popular cloud providers (e.g., GCP) in the CodeCarbon database, making the carbon emission process more accurate in case these platforms are used.

In FedSynthesis, the carbon tracker tool is directly integrated into the client side of the FL setup, allowing CodeCarbon to track emissions for the client-side model training in each round. A participating client, after each round of training, sends reported carbon emission values to the aggregator along with model parameters. In the aggregator, the total mass of the released CO_2 -eq gases is reported, and individual carbon values per client are stored for next-round predictions.

4.3 MLOps Tool

For the MLOps logic, the MLFlow tool³ is incorporated, which is a commonly used, extensive tool with the following capabilities:

- Recording the developed model and parameters, as well as visualization of performance metrics
- Organization of experiments and runs
- Comparison of metrics and parameters across runs

MLFlow does not provide the concept of a “round” which is crucial for an FL setup. To mitigate this issue, the built-in “step” feature of MLFlow is used to collect metrics and parameters in an incremental manner. By setting each round to a step, the collected data are stored on a round basis.

4.4 Carbon Emission Store

Due to the simplicity of the carbon emission data, which consists of a one-dimensional vector of CO_2 -eq values, an in-memory data structure is utilized rather than leveraging an external database component. Thus, the memory space of the client selection application acts as the store.

4.5 The Overall Workflow

Based on the implementation of FedSynthesis, the sequence diagram illustrating the interaction between the system components is given in Figure 2. As one can observe, for each round of the FL process, CodeCarbon starts and stops tracking the carbon emission upon the call of the actual training logic. Afterwards, the reported emission is combined with the model weights and sent to the aggregator on the FL server. Then, on the server side, metrics, params, and possibly the aggregated model, are sent to MLFlow for detailed

Figure 2: The sequence diagram of FedSynthesis workflow

logging. Finally, the gathered CO_2 -eq values are sent to the Client Selector component, where the emissions in the next round are estimated, and depending on the results, a subset of clients is selected based on randomization with carbon-based priorities. This logic is repeated for every FL round.

4.6 Limitations and Discussion

Despite the advantages provided by the proposed framework, FedSynthesis also comes with certain limitations.

4.6.1 Design. By the nature of the design, FedSynthesis can only be used on a centralized FL setup, where the aggregator is on a separate server. This restriction raises the possibility of a single point of failure in case the aggregator is compromised. Adapting FedSynthesis for hierarchical FL architectures is theoretically possible, since there is still a centralized entity that resides at the root in such setups. This adjustment could be achieved by transferring reported carbon emissions up to the root across the intermediary nodes, similar to how weights of local models are transferred. However, adapting FedSynthesis for decentralized FL architectures is not trivial and would require fundamental changes in the design.

4.6.2 Implementation. The current implementation with the chosen components also poses limitations. For instance, CodeCarbon may fail to accurately infer the carbon intensity under certain circumstances. Assume a scenario where the computational device is powered in a special grid fueled by green energy, but the grid itself resides in a country with a relatively higher CI factor. In that case, CodeCarbon, or any other similar carbon tracker tools, will assume a higher CI value than the actual value since it cannot know the characteristics of the power grid.

4.6.3 System Model. Additional restrictions arise due to the adopted system model in which FedSynthesis is designed to work. The major shortcoming in that regard is that the proposed framework

depends on various assumptions that may fail to hold in real-world scenarios. For instance, all FL clients in the process are assumed to have the same networking capability, which would obviously fail in a large wireless network setup comprising heterogeneous devices. Consequently, the assumption that the carbon footprint of client-aggregator communication is negligible compared to the client-side computations might also become invalid in such scenarios. While these assumptions may not harm the adoption of FedSynthesis in cross-silo setups, its applicability in cross-device FL setups requires further evaluation.

Another potential limitation is the framework’s low level of control with regard to the FL process. The system model assumptions enforce a fixed set of configuration parameters, such as the number of communication rounds, the ratio of clients to participate in training, etc. Also, a previously existing deployment is required, meaning that the framework has no freedom over the setup itself. This lack of flexibility might prevent FedSynthesis from achieving higher levels of efficiency under certain circumstances, thereby undermining its effects for complex scenarios.

Despite these limitations of the proposed framework, the value of FedSynthesis can be drawn out in certain scenarios. To fully observe the improvement on carbon footprint, it would be more suitable to consider a geographically diverse setup where FL clients are scattered across different physical locations with a variety of CI factors. One can argue that pre-defining CI values in the FL aggregator would be a much simpler solution. However, when FL clients that execute the training process are actually virtualized resources (e.g., a virtual machine or a container), it is possible that they are migrated to a new physical location between rounds. Such a scenario may allow FedSynthesis to shine with its measurement-based approach, since the framework would be able to handle dynamic CI values thanks to the carbon tracker component. Furthermore, due to the MLOps integration, these changes can be recorded and visualized on a round basis, letting operators know possible issues in a timely manner.

5 An Application of FedSynthesis: GATAKU

As an example use-case, FedSynthesis is applied to GATAKU [16], a previously developed anomaly detection method based on a graph neural network (GNN), for detecting anomalous traffic in a Kubernetes (K8s) environment. GATAKU assumes that the collected network data could be gathered in a single, centralized storage for processing, which raises privacy concerns, as the network traffic may contain sensitive information. However, by leveraging FL, a global ML model can be trained without revealing individual data of nodes. Afterward, FedSynthesis can be applied to preserve the detection performance as high as possible while achieving a visible reduction in the carbon footprint of the FL process.

5.1 Infrastructure Setup

In the original GATAKU setup [16], five VMs comprise the K8s cluster deployed on OpenStack, one of which takes the role of the control-plane and the rest take the role of worker nodes. In this FL setup, an additional node is included for the FL aggregator, acting as the server-side of Flower [3], while the other five nodes comprise the client-side.

Figure 3: A high-level view of the FL setup for GATAKU

A high-level view of the distributed infrastructure, along with the utilized technology stack, is given in Figure 3, where gray lines represent the data flow for each node, and directed green lines represent model weights transmitted between clients and the aggregator. In this setup, clients also upload CO_2 -eq values reported by CodeCarbon and model weights to the server.

5.2 Dataset Collection

To initiate synthetic dataset generation on the GATAKU infrastructure, the same set of applications and attack scenarios used in the original study [16] have been employed. Due to the privacy-sensitive nature of the scenario, each client collects its own dataset and stores the information within its local storage.

Table 2: Dataset characteristics for each client

Node	Size	Benign Samples	Attack Samples
Control-plane	~240 MB	~1,350,000	~145,000
Worker 1	~165 MB	~900,000	~140,000
Worker 2	~370 MB	~2,200,000	~120,000
Worker 3	~135 MB	~750,000	~105,000
Worker 4	~135 MB	~720,000	~160,000
Total	~1 GB	~6,000,000	~570,000

Details regarding local datasets are provided in Table 2. As one can observe, the proportion of benign samples to malicious samples varies significantly among different clients, making the dataset realistic for heterogeneous data cases. For further details on the dataset generation pipeline, the reader is referred to the paper [16].

5.3 Experiments using FedSynthesis

For each of the three developed heuristic carbon reduction algorithms, experiments are performed and results are compared against the standard FedAvg strategy with random client selection [13]. For the evaluation, both the reduction of the overall carbon emission and the effect of client selection on the global model performance are analyzed.

Table 3: Average carbon emission measurement per round for different client selection methods (unit: 10^{-5} kgCO_2)

Method	Mean	Standard Deviation
Non-CO	1.93	0.06
Simple Average	1.75	0.05
Exponential Smoothing	1.84	0.04
Linear Regression	1.79	0.06

Table 4: Shapiro-Wilk test for carbon emission values of different methods

Method	Statistic	p-value
Non-CO	0.9684	0.7206
Simple Avg.	0.9246	0.1216
Exp. Smooth.	0.9324	0.1718
Lin. Reg.	0.9605	0.5545

5.3.1 Carbon Emission Results. Carbon emission values reported for each method, across 20 trials, are provided in Table 3 where “Non-CO” represents the regular FL process without any carbon optimization. As can be seen, all three methods manage to reduce the emitted carbon on a visible level, ranging from 5% to 8% of improvement. In addition, the best reduction ratio is observed by the simple averaging method, which also yields the least standard deviation.

Moreover, a statistical significance test is conducted to assert that the employed techniques indeed improve the carbon footprint of the FL process. To further support the argument in the study, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test [22] is chosen to compare the mean carbon emission per method. ANOVA tests can be considered a generalization of t-tests for scenarios when there are at least three groups to compare. The null hypothesis in the test suggests that there is no significant difference among groups. However, an ANOVA test requires the following conditions: i) in each group, samples should be normally distributed, ii) the variance of samples needs to be about the same among groups.

Shapiro-Wilk test [21] is a common approach for testing whether a group of values is normally distributed, which is the argument indicated by the null hypothesis in the test. For each group in this case, a Shapiro-Wilk test is conducted for the first condition, and results are showcased in Table 4. As one can observe, the p-value for each method is above 12%, indicating that the null hypothesis for each group cannot be rejected, fulfilling the first condition of a Shapiro-Wilk test. Then, the homogeneity of variance condition is considered, and a Levene test [10] is performed to assert that the variance is more or less the same among different methods. The null hypothesis here supports that samples have approximately the same value of variance across groups. Based on the Levene test, a statistic of 0.4738 and a p-value of 0.7015 are acquired, which are too high to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, the second condition of the ANOVA test is fulfilled.

After the validation of the requirements, the ANOVA test is performed with the null hypothesis suggesting that the proposed carbon reduction techniques do not create a significant contribution. A significance level of 0.01 is chosen, and a one-way ANOVA test on carbon emission values is performed. Based on the result of

the test, a statistic of 44.8705 and a p-value of $8.5e-17$, *i.e.*, almost zero, are obtained. Since the p-value is much smaller than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected with a confidence interval of 99%, supporting the argument that there is a significant enhancement of sustainability achieved by leveraging carbon-aware strategies.

Figure 4: Mean f1-score over FL rounds

5.3.2 Impact on the Anomaly Detection Performance. In addition to measuring carbon reduction levels, the impact of incorporating such techniques on the detection performance is also examined. The convergence of the FL-based models is plotted, showing the accuracy metric across rounds, for each carbon-aware client selection method in Figure 4. The figure illustrates that the FL model converges fast after round 10, with most methods. It can be seen that the simple averaging technique makes the model slightly unstable during the initial rounds, even though convergence is achieved roughly after round 15. Moreover, the linear regression-based carbon reduction technique shows the most stable progress, achieving model convergence only after 5 rounds. Since the eventual accuracy after convergence is more or less the same for all techniques, it is that the adoption of different carbon-aware client selection mechanisms has minimal effect on the detection performance.

Table 5: Final accuracy values after 60 rounds, for different client selection methods across 20 trials

Method	Mean	Standard Deviation
Non-CO	0.99846	2.8×10^{-4}
Simple Average	0.99820	4.3×10^{-4}
Exponential Smoothing	0.99833	4.4×10^{-4}
Linear Regression	0.99834	5.7×10^{-4}

The accuracy level reached by the aggregated global model at the end of round 60 is measured for each carbon reduction technique, and results are shown in Table 5. It is observed that the non-carbon-aware version has a slight improvement in accuracy compared to carbon reduction techniques, which is to be expected due to the trade-off between sustainability and model performance. However, since the difference is small, further analysis is required to determine whether such a difference shows any statistical significance.

Figure 5: A sample MLFlow GUI of a 60-round FL run, displaying accuracy, recall, and F1-score over rounds

Table 6: Shapiro-Wilk test for accuracy of different methods

Method	Statistic	p-value
Non-CO	0.8473	0.0048
Simple Average	0.9665	0.6799
Exponential Smoothing	0.9081	0.0587
Linear Regression	0.6845	2.54×10^{-5}

Again, to perform an ANOVA test on accuracy values, it is required to check the normality requirement of ANOVA tests by performing a Shapiro-Wilk test for each method and display the results in Table 6. Both Non-CO and Linear Regression techniques have a p-value of less than 1%, allowing the rejection of the null hypothesis and preventing the utilization of an ANOVA test on accuracy values.

When one of the two requirements of an ANOVA test is not fulfilled, a more flexible and non-parametric variant called Kruskal-Wallis test [9] can be applied. The Kruskal-Wallis test yields a statistic of 3.3151 and a p-value of 0.3455 for the accuracy values of the carbon reduction methods. With such a high p-value, it is not possible to reject the hypothesis which indicates that accuracy values across different groups have the same distribution. As such, it is argued that no major difference in the detection performance arises from the use of proposed carbon reduction techniques.

5.3.3 Investigating Other Metrics via MLFlow. In addition to mean F1-score values, reported per round across all 20 trials, other performance metrics are also examined.

Performance metrics of a randomly chosen trial with a 60-round FL process are provided in Figure 5. One can observe that crucial performance metrics such as accuracy, recall, and f1-score converge rather quickly in Figure 5a-5c. However, the total carbon emission, representing the sum of CO_2-eq emitted by all selected clients in a round, seems to be unstable as illustrated in Figure 5d. However, this volatility can be attributed to various factors, e.g., a different set of clients per round and the current state of the computation units.

5.4 Fairness Analysis

While FedSynthesis aims to provide a carbon-reduced FL process without altering the performance of the constructed global model, it is important that the client selection phase should not be biased

towards a subset of clients. Otherwise, certain clients might dominate the training process, leaving others out and leading to a biased model.

Figure 6: Illustration of the selection frequency of FL clients

To gain an empirical insight into the spectrum of selected FL clients throughout rounds, Figure 6 displays the distribution of chosen clients across 20 trials in the experiment for each developed carbon reduction method. It is observed that while the exponential smoothing technique yields a much more balanced selection, the other two methods give low priority to *Node0*, which acts as the Kubernetes control plane in the testbed. However, note that in each round, three clients out of five are selected to participate in training, and there does not exist a case where a single client dominates the process. This could be attributed to the fact that the carbon-reduced client selection mechanism merely adjusts the probabilities, while the randomness factor still remains.

Table 7: Gini Index of client selection across 20 trials

Method	Mean Counts	Gini Index
Simple Average	[26.45, 36.0, 37.4, 34.25, 31.5]	0.064
Exponential Smoothing	[31.55, 33.6, 33.7, 34.3, 31.75]	0.018
Linear Regression	[28.95, 32.6, 35.45, 36.7, 31.3]	0.048

In addition to selection frequency, as another metric for fairness, Gini Index [7] is used to determine the amount of equality for the client selection process. Table 7 displays, for each carbon reduction method, the Gini Index along with the mean number of participation of FL clients across 20 trials. According to the evaluation, the exponential smoothing technique achieves a Gini value close to zero, indicating almost perfect equality, while the other two methods yield a higher value. Still, in every case, the coefficient is less than 10%, signifying negligible deviation from equality.

While an empirical fairness evaluation is performed for FedSynthesis on the specific use case of GATAKU, a general and theoretical fairness analysis on the framework is left as future work.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, a carbon-aware federated learning framework, namely FedSynthesis, is designed to reduce the carbon footprint of FL pipelines. An implementation using Flower framework, CodeCarbon, and MLFlow is provided. The flexible design allows users to implement their carbon estimation methods tailored to their own use cases. Then, FedSynthesis is applied to an existing machine learning model, namely GATAKU, and conducted experiments reveal that FedSynthesis manages to reduce carbon emissions by about 5% to 8%, without significantly sacrificing the model performance.

As future work, it is planned to increase the number of use-case applications and the number of experiments on which to test FedSynthesis, to strengthen the practicality of the framework. Moreover, a more analytical and scenario-agnostic fairness evaluation should be conducted for the proposed client selection mechanisms to ensure that no major bias is introduced that would degrade the performance of the constructed model. Lastly, the framework will be developed further to loosen up the assumptions made in this study, especially the inclusion of communication between clients and the aggregator in the carbon emission calculation.

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